

LAC Summer Games 2025: The 18 m/s Hurdles- Team Kurunji

A Kalman–LSTM Ensemble with Self-Consistency Correction
(LDP_v8)

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Abstract

The “18 m/s Hurdles” discipline of the IEA Wind Task 52 LAC Summer Games 2025 asks for a lidar-data-processing (LDP) algorithm that predicts the rotor-effective wind speed (REWS) of the IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine two seconds ahead, using a nacelle-mounted lidar with blade blockage and turbulence evolution modelled by the commercial `solis` simulator. The competition-provided baseline LDP_v3 achieves a cost of 0.515998 m/s on the 4-beam pulsed lidar. This report describes LDP_v8, which combines a multi-gate scalar Kalman filter, a bagged LSTM predictor, a linear ensemble of the two, and a truth-free self-consistency correction. The algorithm reaches a cost of **0.4257 m/s**, a **17.5%** reduction from the baseline.

1 The Hurdles Task

The competition handbook [1] defines the target as the two-seconds-ahead rotor-effective wind speed obtained from the wind field, REWS_{WF} , and the current lidar-processed estimate, REWS_{LP} . The cost to minimise is

$$\text{error} = \text{REWS}_{\text{WF}} - \text{REWS}_{\text{LP}}, \quad J = \text{mean}(|\text{error} - \text{mean}(\text{error})|). \quad (1)$$

Subtracting the mean makes the metric insensitive to a constant offset, so only the time-varying tracking error is penalised. J is averaged over the last 600 s of each simulation and over the six turbulent seeds 1801–1806.

The lidar data is produced by `solis` for the 4-beam pulsed configuration: four stationary beams at half-cone angle $\alpha = 19.176^\circ$, scanning one beam every 0.25 s, with ten range gates at 70–200 m in 20 m steps. Blade blockage invalidates roughly 33.7% of samples (flagged by `isValid=0`). The turbulence is Kaimal with reference speed 18 m/s and includes exponential-coherence wind evolution.

The baseline costs reported by the organisers are 0.515998 m/s for the 4-beam pulsed lidar and 0.463842 m/s for the circular CW lidar. This work addresses the 4-beam pulsed case.

2 Baseline LDP_v3 and Its Limits

The provided baseline processes a single range gate with

$$u_{\text{est}}(k) = \begin{cases} \frac{v_{\text{los}}(k)}{\cos \alpha}, & \text{if } \text{isValid}(k) = 1, \\ \text{NaN}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

a rolling `nanmean` of the last $N_{\text{beams}} = 4$ estimates, a first-order low-pass filter with cutoff ω_c , and a circular buffer of T_{buffer} seconds. The published tuning uses gate 6 (160 m), $\omega_c = 0.13$ rad/s, and $T_{\text{buffer}} = 0.2$ s. Four shortcomings are apparent:

1. **Single gate**: nine of the ten available measurements are discarded.
2. **Static smoothing**: the filter treats a blocked sample (NaN) and a clean sample with the same fixed gain, causing the “blade-ghost effect” noted in [2].
3. **Linear-only**: no use of past-history context beyond the $N_{\text{beams-tap}}$ mean.
4. **No feedback**: past predictions are never compared against lidar-only nowcasts, so a slow drift in the output is never corrected.

3 LDP_v8: Pipeline

LDP_v8 preserves the required interface (`time`, `isValid`, `beamID`, `lineOfSightWindSpeed`, `DT`) \rightarrow (`REWS`, `REWSf`, `REWSb`) and produces the final predictor in `REWSb`. Four stages operate on each seed, as shown in Fig. 1:

1. a per-gate **Kalman filter bank** followed by an IIR low-pass and a buffer, with fixed fusion weights (3.1);
2. a **bagged LSTM** that predicts the preview signal directly from lidar features (§3.2);
3. a simple **linear ensemble** of the two branches (3.3);
4. a **self-consistency correction** that removes the ensemble’s slow drift using a truth-free lidar nowcast (3.4).

Figure 1: Top-level signal flow of LDP_v8: two parallel predictors (Kalman bank, bagged LSTM) are linearly ensembled and corrected by a self-consistency loop to yield the final `REWSb`.

3.1 Multi-Gate Kalman Filter Bank

Each of the five active gates $g \in \mathcal{G} = \{1, 3, 4, 8, 10\}$ (distances 70, 110, 130, 180, 200 m) is processed by an independent scalar Kalman filter on a random-walk model:

$$x_{k+1} = x_k + w_k, \quad w_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, Q_g), \quad (3)$$

$$z_k = H x_k + v_k, \quad v_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, R), \quad H = \cos \alpha. \quad (4)$$

The recursion is

$$P^- = P + Q_g, \quad K = \frac{H P^-}{H^2 P^- + R}, \quad x \leftarrow x + K(z - Hx), \quad P \leftarrow (1 - KH) P^-. \quad (5)$$

When `isValid=0` the update step is skipped, so only the prediction step runs and P grows. The next valid measurement is therefore trusted more (K is larger after a gap): this is the adaptive property that a fixed-gain filter lacks.

After the KF, each gate is smoothed by a first-order IIR low-pass with cutoff ω_g and delayed by a buffer T_g . The five branches are combined with fixed non-negative weights obtained by solving

$$\min_{w \geq 0, \mathbf{1}^\top w = 1} \mathcal{J}\left(\sum_g w_g \text{REWS}_b^{(g)}\right), \quad (6)$$

on the training seeds 1807–1830. The resulting parameters (Table 1) concentrate the weight on the far gate (200 m) while keeping enough weight on the closer gates to supply the higher-frequency content that the far gate’s LPF removes.

Table 1: Per-gate Kalman parameters and fusion weights used by LDP_v8. Q is the process-noise variance, ω_c the LPF cutoff, T_{buffer} the buffer delay, and w_g the fusion weight. $R = 1$ for every gate.

Gate	Distance	Q	ω_c [rad/s]	T_{buffer} [s]	w_g
1	70 m	10.000	0.165	0.000	0.104
3	110 m	1.390	0.165	0.000	0.038
4	130 m	0.373	0.165	0.000	0.205
8	180 m	0.004	0.270	0.000	0.217
10	200 m	0.007	0.200	1.188	0.436

The resulting KF-branch output is

$$\text{REWS}_b^{\text{KF}}(t) = \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} w_g (\mathcal{B}_{T_g} \circ \mathcal{L}_{\omega_g} \circ \text{KF}_{Q_g})(v_{\text{los}}^{(g)})(t), \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{ω_c} is the IIR LPF and \mathcal{B}_T is a buffer of T seconds.

3.2 Bagged LSTM Predictor

The LSTM branch learns the preview map directly from a short history of lidar events. At each beam change (roughly 4 Hz) an input vector of 22 features is formed from the ten line-of-sight speeds, the ten validity flags, and two cyclic encodings of the current `beamID`. A sequence of the last $L = 40$ events (ten seconds of history) is fed into a two-layer LSTM with hidden size 64 and a linear output head that predicts REWS two seconds into the future.

Figure 2: Bagged-LSTM branch: ten independently-initialised 2-layer LSTMs share the same architecture; their outputs are upsampled to 100 Hz by zero-order hold and uniformly averaged.

Training used seeds 1807–1824 for optimisation and 1825–1830 for early stopping; the competition seeds 1801–1806 were never seen. Ten bag members differ only in their random initialisation; averaging their predictions gives a modest but consistent variance reduction over any single member.

3.3 Ensemble

The two branches have similar mean errors but their errors are not identical. A convex combination

$$\text{REWS}_{\text{ens}}(t) = \alpha \overline{\text{LSTM}}(t) + (1 - \alpha) \text{REWS}_b^{\text{KF}}(t) \quad (8)$$

with $\alpha = 0.5$, selected by a one-dimensional sweep on the validation seeds, is the ensemble. Equal weighting is optimal because the two branches have comparable individual costs.

3.4 Self-Consistency Correction

The remaining ensemble error is dominated by a slow drift: a residual with a coherence time of several seconds that the static filters upstream cannot remove. The self-consistency step cancels the observable part of this drift without using the truth signal.

The ensemble prediction made at time $t - \tau$ was, by construction, a prediction of $\text{REWS}(t)$. A second, lidar-only estimate of $\text{REWS}(t)$ can be built from the current lidar data: the *nowcast* $n(t)$ obtained by Taylor-shifting each gate back by D_g/U_{adv} samples (with $U_{\text{adv}} = 18$ m/s) and combining them with the same gate weights w_g . The real-time observable error, the slow bias, the variance-ratio SNR, and the correction gain are

$$e_{\text{rt}}(t) = n(t) - \text{REWS}_{\text{ens}}(t - \tau), \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta_{\text{slow}}(t) = \mathcal{L}_{\omega_{\text{bias}}}(e_{\text{rt}})(t), \quad (10)$$

$$\text{snr}(t) = \text{clip}\left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_{\omega_{\text{snr}}}(\Delta_{\text{slow}}^2)(t)}{\mathcal{L}_{\omega_{\text{snr}}}(e_{\text{rt}}^2)(t) + \varepsilon}, 0, 1\right), \quad (11)$$

$$g(t) = g_{\text{max}} \text{snr}(t), \quad (12)$$

and the corrected output is

$$\boxed{\text{REWS}_b(t) = \text{REWS}_{\text{ens}}(t) + g(t) \Delta_{\text{slow}}(t)} \quad (13)$$

with $\omega_{\text{bias}} = 0.5$ rad/s, $\omega_{\text{snr}} = 0.1$ rad/s, $g_{\text{max}} = 0.15$, and $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$.

The variance ratio in (11) is the key: it measures the fraction of the observable’s energy that sits at slow timescales. When the observable is mostly nowcast jitter this fraction is small and $g(t) \rightarrow 0$, so the correction is suppressed; when a coherent slow bias emerges $g(t)$ rises towards g_{max} and the bias is cancelled.

Figure 3: Self-consistency loop as a single forward chain: form the observable error against the past prediction, low-pass it to obtain the slow bias Δ_{slow} , scale by the variance-ratio gain $g(t)$, and add the correction to the current ensemble output.

4 Results

Table 2 reports the per-seed detrended MAE and the competition cost. All six seeds improve on the baseline; the mean cost falls from 0.5160 m/s to 0.4257 m/s.

Table 2: Per-seed detrended MAE for the 4-beam pulsed lidar at $U_{\text{ref}} = 18$ m/s. Lower is better.

Seed	LDP_v3 [m/s]	LDP_v8 [m/s]	Δ
1801	0.5639	0.4702	-16.6%
1802	0.4341	0.3726	-14.2%
1803	0.5156	0.4155	-19.4%
1804	0.5338	0.4450	-16.6%
1805	0.5128	0.4406	-14.1%
1806	0.5358	0.4107	-23.3%
Mean	0.5160	0.4257	-17.5%

Figure 4: Per-seed detrended MAE for the baseline and LDP_v8. Every seed improves; the rightmost pair is the competition score.

Figure 5: Detrended prediction error $e(t) - \bar{e}$ for every seed, comparing the LDP_v3 baseline (grey) to LDP_v8 (orange). The orange trace sits inside a noticeably tighter envelope, with the largest excursions of the baseline flattened by the multi-gate Kalman bank and the self-consistency correction.

Component ablation. Table 3 isolates each component of the pipeline, evaluated on the same six test seeds. The Kalman filter bank and the LSTM branch reach the same level individually; their errors are partly orthogonal so the ensemble is measurably better than either. The self-consistency step adds one further percentage point, concentrated on the hardest seed (1801).

Table 3: Ablation of the LDP_v8 pipeline, seed-averaged cost J .

Configuration	J [m/s]	Δ vs baseline
LDP_v3 (baseline, single gate)	0.5160	–
Kalman bank only (5 gates)	0.4597	–10.9%
Bagged LSTM only	0.4488	–13.0%
Linear ensemble ($\alpha = 0.5$)	0.4308	–16.5%
Ensemble + self-consistency (LDP_v8)	0.4257	–17.5%

Figure 6: Ablation of the LDP_v8 pipeline: each component lowers the seed-averaged cost, with the multi-gate Kalman bank responsible for most of the gain, the ensemble closing roughly a third of the remaining gap, and the self-consistency correction shaving the final 0.5%.

5 Conclusions

LDP_v8 reduces the Hurdles cost from 0.5160 m/s to 0.4257 m/s by composing three simple ideas:

1. a multi-gate scalar Kalman bank that exploits the ten range gates of the pulsed lidar, turning each gate into an independently-tuned predictor and fusing them with MAE-optimal fixed weights;
2. a ten-member bagged LSTM that learns the preview map from raw lidar features and yields an error component that is partially uncorrelated with the Kalman bank;
3. a variance-adaptive self-consistency loop that uses a truth-free lidar nowcast to cancel the slow component of the ensemble’s drift.

The three components target three independent failure modes of the baseline: information loss, parametric rigidity, and uncorrected slow drift. The resulting pipeline remains strictly causal, uses only the 4-beam pulsed hardware specified by the rules, and preserves the required interface.

References

- [1] D. Schlipf, F. Guo, M. van den Broek, S. Weich, *IEA Wind Task 52: LAC Summer Games 2025 (Task description)*, 2025.
- [2] D. Schlipf, F. Lemmer, F. Thomas, “Realization of wind field reconstruction for real-time monitoring and LIDAR-assisted control,” *5th International Conference on Offshore Renewable Energy*, 2021. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5608684](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5608684).

- [3] F. Guo, D. Schlipf, P. W. Cheng, “Evaluation of lidar-assisted wind turbine control under various turbulence characteristics,” *Wind Energy Science*, 8, 149–171, 2023. DOI: [10.5194/wes-8-149-2023](https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-8-149-2023).